

LINEAR PREDICTION FOR 2-D VECTOR RANDOM FIELDS

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Abstract

Linear prediction for two-dimensional (2-D) multichannel signals is discussed. Such data occurs in remote sensing applications, in the analysis of color images, and in other areas. This paper deals with representation of this data, the general form of the Normal equations, issues of separability, and some results that relate multichannel linear prediction problems to multidimensional linear prediction problems.

INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with linear prediction for two-dimensional (2-D) multichannel or vector-valued signal data. Such data can occur in remote sensing applications, in the analysis of color images, and in array processing. The signals are represented by a vector valued random field $\mathbf{F}(n, m)$ sampled on a rectangular lattice. Conceptually one can think of this data as a set of stacked planes of 2-D signal data as shown in Fig. 1. In the case of images each plane may represent some image component, such as a color component, and the components are assumed to be in pixel registration. The equations of linear prediction can be written as a filtering operation

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}}(n, m) = - \sum_i \sum_j \mathbf{A}_{ij} \mathbf{F}(n-i, m-j) \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ is the predicted value at coordinates n and m , the \mathbf{A}_{ij} are a set of matrix filter coefficients, and the sum is taken over some 2-D region of support. Correlations

exist both *within* channels and *between* channels and the equations of linear prediction reflect all of these correlations. This paper deals with the general form of the Normal equations, some results that relate multichannel linear prediction problems to multidimensional linear prediction problems, and issues of separability.

Fig. 1 2-D multichannel signal data

DATA REPRESENTATION AND NORMAL EQUATIONS

The data to be analyzed is assumed to be stationary and is represented as vectors for purposes of computing statistics and writing equations of linear prediction. The data at each coordinate location (n, m) is treated as a vector quantity with dimension P equal to the number of channels. These vectors are organized first by rows and then

by columns into a larger vector which is then the lexicographic vector representation of the data.

Normal equations corresponding to (1) can be written as

$$\mathbf{R} \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{S} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the covariance matrix for the data, \mathbf{A} is an appropriately ordered matrix of the filter coefficients, and \mathbf{S} contains a single non-zero block \mathbf{K}_w which is the prediction error covariance. The matrix \mathbf{R} has three levels of partitioning and for any (causal, semicausal, or noncausal) rectangular region of support is block Toeplitz with block Toeplitz blocks.

For a first quadrant filter with $N \times M$ region of support the Normal equations (2) have the specific form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}(0) & \mathbf{R}(-1) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(-N+1) \\ \mathbf{R}(1) & \mathbf{R}(0) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(-N+2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}(N-1) & \mathbf{R}(N-2) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}^{(0)} \\ \mathbf{A}^{(1)} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{A}^{(N-1)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}^{(0)} \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}(n) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}(n,0) & \mathbf{R}(n,-1) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(n,-M+1) \\ \mathbf{R}(n,1) & \mathbf{R}(n,0) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(n,-M+2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}(n,M-1) & \mathbf{R}(n,M-2) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(n,0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

and where $\mathbf{R}(n,m)$ is the matrix correlation function

$$\mathbf{R}(n,m) = E \{ \mathbf{F}(n',m') \mathbf{F}^T(n'-n,m'-m) \} \quad (5)$$

The quantities $\mathbf{A}^{(n)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(0)}$ are defined by

$$\mathbf{A}^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{n,0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{n,1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{A}_{n,M-1} \end{bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{S}^{(0)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_w \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6a,b)$$

with $\mathbf{A}_{0,0} = \mathbf{I}$ and where \mathbf{K}_w is the prediction error covariance

$$\mathbf{K}_w = E \{ (\mathbf{F} - \hat{\mathbf{F}})(\mathbf{F} - \hat{\mathbf{F}})^T \} \quad (7)$$

The covariance matrix in (3) has the doubly block Toeplitz structure described above. The innermost blocks are not Toeplitz however and the the matrix is not block symmetric at any level. Solution of (3) gives the coefficients $\mathbf{A}_{i,j}$ for $(i,j) \neq (0,0)$ and \mathbf{K}_w .

RELATIONS TO OTHER LINEAR PREDICTION PROBLEMS

Relation to the 3-D Problem.

There is a close connection between the single channel 2-D linear prediction problem and the multichannel 1-D linear prediction problem [1]. Similar but more general relations exist in higher dimensions. If we multiply both sides of (3) by a P-dimensional vector \mathbf{a}_{00} and define

$$\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{S}^{(0)} \mathbf{a}_{00} \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{A}^{(i)} \mathbf{a}_{00} \quad (8b)$$

then we are led to the equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}(0) & \mathbf{R}(-1) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(-N+1) \\ \mathbf{R}(1) & \mathbf{R}(0) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(-N+2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}(N-1) & \mathbf{R}(N-2) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_0 \\ \mathbf{a}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{a}_{N-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}_0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

If we further define $\mathbf{a}_n^T = (\mathbf{a}_{n0}^T, \mathbf{a}_{n1}^T, \dots, \mathbf{a}_{nM-1}^T)$ and $\mathbf{s}_0^T = (\sigma^2 \boldsymbol{\iota}_P^T, 0^T, \dots, 0^T)$ where $\mathbf{a}_{nm}^T = (a_{nm0}, a_{nm1}, \dots, a_{nmP-1})^T$ with $a_{000} = 1$ and where $\boldsymbol{\iota}_P$ is the P-dimensional vector $(1, 0, 0, \dots, 0)^T$, then (9) represents the Normal equations for the 3-D linear prediction problem

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}}(n,m,p) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \sum_{k=0}^{P-1} a_{ijk} F(n-i, m-j, p-k) \quad (i,j,k) \neq (0,0,0) \quad (10)$$

and $\sigma^2 = E \{ (F - \hat{F})^2 \}$ is the prediction error variance. The covariance matrix appearing on the left side of (9) is defined in (3)-(5) where in this case the vectors \mathbf{F} are $(F(n,m,0), F(n,m,1), \dots, F(n,m,P-1))^T$.

With these definitions (8a) and (8b) are equivalent to

$$\mathbf{K}_W \mathbf{a}_{00} = \sigma^2 \mathbf{L}_P \quad (11a)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{ij} = \mathbf{A}_{ij} \mathbf{a}_{00} \quad (11b)$$

Equation (11a) is a set of Normal equations in 1-D that can be solved for \mathbf{a}_{00} and σ^2 although \mathbf{K}_W is not Toeplitz in general. Equation (11b) determines the rest of the \mathbf{a}_{ij} .

The result can be summarized in this way. The 3-D linear prediction problem with Normal equations (9) can be expressed as a 2-D multichannel problem and a 1-D single channel problem whose Normal equations are given by (3) and (11a) respectively. After the equations for these two subproblems have been solved, the filter coefficients for the 3-D problem are given by the reduction operation (8b) or (11b).

Since the 3-D filter parameters have the form (11b) one can view the computation of the 3-D prediction error as performed by a cascade of two filters. The first is a multichannel 2-D filter that produces a P-dimensional error vector; the second is a single channel 1-D filter with parameters \mathbf{a}_{00} that is applied across channels. The transfer function of the 3-D filter can be expressed in terms of the lower order components as

$$H(z_1, z_2, z_3) = \mathbf{a}_{00}^T \mathbf{H}_{MC}(z_1, z_2) \mathbf{z}_3 \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{H}_{MC} is the transfer function of the 2-D multichannel filter and \mathbf{z}_3 is the vector $(1, z_3, z_3^2, \dots, z_3^{P-1})^T$. This expression follows easily from (11b).

Decomposition of the 2-D Multichannel Problem. It is further possible to express the 2-D multichannel problem as the combination of two 1-D linear prediction problems. The first of these is a 1-D multichannel problem where the channels are organized into an array of size M by P. This shown in Fig. 2. The second is also a multichannel problem where linear prediction is applied across the M channels to compute a P-dimensional prediction error vector (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 2-D multichannel decomposition

The first MP-channel linear prediction problem can be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}}_n = - \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \alpha^{(i)} \mathbf{f}_{n-i} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{f}_n is the MP-dimensional data vector and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_n$ is its estimate. The coefficients $\alpha^{(n)}$ have the form

$$\alpha^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{00}^{(n)} & \alpha_{01}^{(n)} & \dots & \alpha_{M-1,0}^{(n)} \\ \alpha_{10}^{(n)} & \alpha_{11}^{(n)} & \dots & \alpha_{M-1,1}^{(n)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \alpha_{M-1,0}^{(n)} & \alpha_{M-1,1}^{(n)} & \dots & \alpha_{M-1,M-1}^{(n)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

where each block $\alpha_{i,j}^{(n)}$ is of size $P \times P$. The $\alpha^{(n)}$ are found by solving

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}(0) & \mathbf{R}(-1) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(-N+1) \\ \mathbf{R}(1) & \mathbf{R}(0) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(-N+2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}(N-1) & \mathbf{R}(N-2) & \dots & \mathbf{R}(0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ \alpha^{(1)} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{(N-1)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma^{(0)} \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where $\Sigma^{(0)}$ is the prediction error covariance and where the covariance matrix appearing

on the left side of (15) is the same as that in (3). Since this is a 1-D problem the multichannel Levinson recursion can be used to find the $\alpha^{(n)}$ and $\Sigma^{(0)}$. A comparison of (3) and (15) shows that the coefficients for the multichannel 2-D problem can then be found by solving

$$\Sigma^{(0)} \mathbf{A}^{(0)} = \mathbf{S}^{(0)} \quad (16a)$$

and computing

$$\mathbf{A}^{(i)} = \alpha^{(i)} \mathbf{A}^{(0)} \quad (16b)$$

Equation (16a) represents the Normal equations corresponding to the second linear prediction problem.

Since the 3-D linear prediction problem can be decomposed into a 1-D problem and a 2-D multichannel problem, and the 2-D multichannel problem can be broken down into two 1-D multichannel problems, the 3-D problem can be formulated as a series of 1-D linear prediction problems.

SEPARABLE 2-D MULTICHANNEL PROBLEMS

When the covariance matrix for the 2-D vector random fields is separable, various simplifications result. In all cases (2) reduces to a simpler set of Normal equations. The results are summarized here.

When the correlation *within* channels is separable from the correlation *between* channels the covariance matrix \mathbf{R} in (2) can be represented as the direct product of a between-channel covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_P and a within-channel covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_{RC} . In this case we can postulate a separable form for the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{S} and show that they provide a solution to the original Normal equations. In particular, using \times to represent the direct product, we can write

$$(\mathbf{R}_P \times \mathbf{R}_{RC})(\mathbf{I}_P \times \mathbf{a}_{RC}) = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{RC}^2} \mathbf{K}_W\right) \times \sigma_{RC}^2 \boldsymbol{\nu}_{NM} \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{I}_P is the $P \times P$ identity matrix, \mathbf{a}_{RC}

is an NM -dimensional vector whose first component is 1, and $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{NM}$ is the NM -dimensional vector $(1,0,0,\dots,0)^T$. Then (17) implies the two relations

$$\mathbf{R}_{RC} \mathbf{a}_{RC} = \sigma_{RC}^2 \boldsymbol{\nu}_{NM} \quad (18a)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_W = \sigma_{RC}^2 \mathbf{R}_P \quad (18b)$$

Since the solution of (2) is unique, this shows that it can be found from (18). The form of (17) indicates that each channel has the same filter coefficients \mathbf{a}_{RC} and that there are no between-channel terms. The parameters \mathbf{a}_{RC} and σ_{RC}^2 are obtained by solving the Normal equations (18a) pertaining to a single channel 2-D problem. Then from (18b), the prediction error covariance for the 2-D multichannel problem is a scaled version of the between-channel covariance. The scale factor is the single channel prediction error variance.

Similar results can be obtained if the covariance is separable along rows and columns. In this case the covariance matrix can be represented by the direct product of a matrix \mathbf{R}_{CP} which relates to a 1-D multichannel process along the columns and a matrix \mathbf{R}_R representing a 1-D single channel process along the rows. The postulated solution is of the form

$$(\mathbf{R}_{CP} \times \mathbf{R}_R)(\mathbf{A}_{CP} \times \mathbf{a}_R) = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_R^2} \mathbf{S}^{(0)}\right) \times \sigma_R^2 \boldsymbol{\nu}_M \quad (19)$$

which implies

$$\mathbf{R}_{CP} \mathbf{A}_{CP} = \frac{1}{\sigma_R^2} \mathbf{S}^{(0)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_N \\ 0 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20a)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_R \mathbf{a}_R = \sigma_R^2 \boldsymbol{\nu}_N \quad (20b)$$

Equation (20a) is a set of Normal equations for a 1-D multichannel problem which we

solve for the prediction matrices \mathbf{A}_{CF} and the prediction error covariance \mathbf{E}_N . Equation (20b) represents Normal equations for a 1-D single channel problem that we solve for the filter parameters \mathbf{a}_R and the prediction error variance σ_R^2 . The solution of these two sets of Normal equations then allows us to compute the filter coefficients as $\mathbf{A}_{CP} \times \mathbf{a}_R$ and the error covariance as

$$\mathbf{K}_W = \sigma_R^2 \mathbf{E}_N \quad (21)$$

In the case where the covariance matrix in (2) is completely separable, along rows and columns and between channels, we have $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_C \times \mathbf{R}_R \times \mathbf{R}_P$. Then we are led to the two 1-D single channel subproblems

$$\mathbf{R}_R \mathbf{a}_R = \sigma_R^2 \mathbf{1}_N \quad (22a)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_C \mathbf{a}_C = \sigma_C^2 \mathbf{1}_M \quad (22b)$$

and the 2-D multichannel parameters are computed from

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}_P \times \mathbf{a}_C \times \mathbf{a}_R \quad (23a)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_W = \sigma_R^2 \sigma_C^2 \mathbf{R}_P \quad (23b)$$

Observe that for the separable cases discussed in this section, all of the subproblems defined in the previous section involve Toeplitz covariance matrices when the data is stationary. These separable cases may be the only cases in which (11a) and (16a) involve Toeplitz matrices.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper discussed the 2-D multichannel linear prediction problem and the form of the associated Normal equations. It was shown that the 3-D linear prediction problem could be viewed as the combination of a 2-D multichannel problem and a 1-D single channel problem. Further the 2-D multichannel problem could be formulated as a sequence of two 1-D multichannel problems. Thus the 3-D problem could be viewed as a series of 1-D linear prediction problems.

Various types of separability were explored for the 2-D multichannel problem.

When the correlation is separable to within-channel and between-channel components the within-channel parameters are identical for each channel and the multichannel prediction error covariance is proportional to the between-channel covariance matrix. When the problem is separable along rows and columns a 1-D multichannel and a 1-D single channel problem result. The filter parameters are found by forming a direct product of the parameters for these two subproblems and the prediction error covariance is the product of those for the subproblems.

When the correlation is separable along rows, columns, and between planes, two 1-D single channel problems result. Filter coefficients are identical within each channel and are equal to the product of the filter coefficients for the row and column subproblems. The prediction error covariance is a scaled version of the given between-plane covariance matrix.

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References

- [1] C.W. Therrien, "Relations Between 2-D and Multichannel Linear Prediction," *IEEE Trans. Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, Vol. ASSP-29, No. 3, June 1981